

Analysis of local journal metric relationships within an R1 university Collection

William H. Mischo¹ and Mary C. Schlembach²

¹*w-mischo@illinois.edu*

Grainger Engineering Library Information Center, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign Library, Champaign, IL (USA)

²*schlemba@illinois.edu*

Chemistry Library, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign Library, Champaign, IL (USA)

Abstract

This paper examines the correlational relationships between local journal authorship, local and external citation counts, full-text downloads, link-resolver clicks, and four global journal impact factor indices within an all-disciplines journal collection of 12,200 titles and several subject subsets at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign (UIUC) Library. Earlier investigations of the relationships between usage (downloads) and citation metrics have been inconclusive, but the preliminary results of this study show strong correlations in the all-disciplines set and most subject subsets. Normalized Eigenfactor was the only global impact factor index that correlated highly with local journal metrics. Some of the subject disciplines' variations may be explained by the journal publication aspirations of UIUC researchers where faculty are unable to publish in the most highly cited or heavily downloaded journals.

Introduction

A number of studies have examined the relationships and patterns involving local journal publication, citation, and usage metrics. Many of these studies have examined the relationships between citation and usage, in both local and global settings, beginning with print collections, and, with the widespread adoption of e-journals, moving to online citations and download usage. Research relating to this topic appears in both the library and informetrics literature.

Determining these local journal metric relationships, particularly in the form of correlational values between individual journal title publication, citation, and usage metrics are valuable for several reasons. The value indicators can serve to inform a library's collection development and collection management decisions, specifically journal subscription and retention decisions. From a subject liaison perspective, this data can be used to construct a knowledgebase identifying departmental and faculty research concentrations and areas of focus. The data can also be utilized in the generation of a

library's core journal list, which can provide an evidence-based listing of journals necessary to meet

the instructional and research needs of the library's primary constituents. In this way, journal metric data can be used to indicate if the collection is adequately supporting the research and instructional needs of faculty and students. Collecting and correlating authorship, citation, and usage data can also allow patterns of journal value to emerge, resulting in a more accurate picture of journal value than cost-per-use calculations or other methods.

From a research standpoint, libraries are also interested in determining the degree to which any one of the local journal metrics, particularly full-text downloads or local citations, can be used as a proxy for predicting any of the other values. This might allow, for example, predictive statements about publication numbers or citations to be made from usage numbers, or vice versa, and for one measure to serve as a predictive proxy for another measure. If this were uniformly the case, libraries could focus on collecting one or two types of measurements and, from these selected metrics, they could be certain that the other local metrics could be accurately predicted.

Methodology

This paper examines the relationships between specific local journal publication, citation, usage, and impact metrics from 17,934 journals in all disciplines, including 12,200 active titles, gathered from scholarly activities involving researchers at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign (UIUC), a Carnegie R1 university. We are analysing and calculating the correlations over five years of local journal authorship numbers; five years of local and external citation counts; two years of full-text downloads, two years of link-resolver data, and the values from four global journal impact factor indices. We also examined correlation pair values for the journals in several specific subject areas, including engineering, life sciences, the social sciences, chemistry, and history and philosophy. For the usage data, the study utilized the publisher-provided COUNTER full-text download usage reports from the thirty-five commercial and professional publishers and four aggregators –

EBSCO, ProQuest, Ovid, and JSTOR. There were 10,604 of the 17,934 journals in the LJUR all-discipline corpus that had COUNTER download numbers available and 9,190 of the 12,300 active journal titles with available download data, so the COUNTER statistics covered a high majority of the journal titles in the study.

The correlation processing was set up to examine nine journal metric indicators: the LJUR supplied local authorship, LJUR local citation, LJUR external citation, full-text COUNTER download usage, link resolver clickthrough results, and four global journal impact service indexes. The correlation analyses were conducted over the complete all-discipline set of 12,200 journal titles and five subsets.

Results

Three of the global journal impact measures -- ISI JCR, SNIP, and SJR -- exhibited a non-significant R value with the publication, citation, and usage measures for the cohort of journals in the study. This reinforces the results obtained in earlier studies that show that the ISI JCR is not a useful measure for local citation and publication activities and typically cannot serve as a proxy for local scholarly communication measures. Only the normalized Eigenfactor values were used in the remaining analysis.

Table 1 shows the correlation results from the 12,200 active journal titles and journal value indicators for the all-disciplines analysis. Of the fifteen pairwise value combinations (six items taken two at a time), only three Pearson R values are below 0.5.

Table 1: Correlation Results from 12,200 active journal titles in all Disciplines					
	Outside Cited	Articles Written	Downloads	SFX Clicks	Normalized Eigenfactor
Locally Cited	N= 12200 R=0.761	N= 12200 R=0.769	N= 9190 R=0.784	N= 11709 R=0.586	N= 8408 R=0.785
Outside Cited		N= 12200 R=0.790	N= 9190 R=0.495	N= 11709 R=0.435	N= 8408 R=0.642
Articles written			N= 9190 R=0.528	N= 11709 R=0.494	N= 8408 R=0.593
Downloads of articles				N= 9041 R=0.729	N= 6189 R=0.816
SFX Clicks					N= 8075 R=0.729

Several specific disciplinary correlations exhibited interesting differences with the all-discipline analysis, particularly in three pairwise relationships: *downloads* and *locally cited*; *articles written* and *locally cited*; and *downloads* and *articles written*. Researchers are citing the most relevant and important articles in their field and faculty and students are downloading the most relevant articles for their research and instruction. For downloads and citations, there appears to be a high correlation between the two in specialized fields in which the readers tend to be the active researchers but in fields where the reader population is wider and more diverse than the research community, the correlations are lower. It is also the case that some lesser academic articles in more general journals are being downloaded for classroom use and not research.

Faculty are citing the most important articles in the most prestigious journals in the bibliographies of their research and, at the same time, are trying to have their research published in those most prestigious journals. Research faculty aspire to be published in the same journals that are publishing the most highly cited articles. The all-discipline correlation between the two indicators *articles written* and *locally cited* is very high at R=0.7698 and that shows a significant university-wide ability to publish in the same journals that are being cited. But the correlation varies across the six subsets. The *articles written* and *locally cited* correlations in the subject discipline subsets examined in this study match closely with the associated program rankings in the U.S. News and World Report 2022 Graduate School Rankings. The prestige of a department or program might be measured by the strength of the correlation between a faculty group's *articles written* and their *locally cited* indicator pair.

The aspirational publishing aspect may also affect the correlations between the indicators *downloads* and *articles written*.

While earlier investigations have proven inconclusive, this study shows strong correlations in the all-disciplines set and most subject subsets between full-text downloads and local citations.

Within the all-disciplines 12,200 active journals, and in most subject disciplines, this study's correlation results do imply that download measurements can predict local citations and vice versa.